

Measuring spatial congruence in the school-neighborhood nexus

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July 29, 2025

Abstract

This research addresses the critical need for a comprehensive understanding of the spatial dynamics between public schools and residential neighborhoods, both of which significantly influence children’s life outcomes. The study introduces innovative methodologies for examining the spatial relationships between school catchment areas and neighborhoods through geodemographic clustering and spatial congruence measures. By applying these methods to the largest 110 metropolitan areas in the United States, encompassing 24,507 elementary school catchments and 17,608 neighborhoods, the research provides novel insights into how these spatial interactions affect ethnoracial integration and educational diversity. The findings reveal the potential of targeted policy interventions that leverage these spatial relationships to promote equity and reduce segregation in educational settings, thereby offering a valuable framework for policymakers to improve access to opportunities across diverse communities.

1 Introduction

Residential neighborhoods and educational environments significantly influence various human development outcomes, including academic success. Both neighborhoods and schools, as spatial entities, shape the distribution of institutional resources and social interactions, which contribute to observed differences in outcomes. Despite recognizing their

independent and interdependent impacts, our understanding of the spatial relationship between these contexts is limited, and formal analyses of this nexus are rare (Galster, 2001).

As interest in improving access to opportunities grows, addressing this knowledge gap becomes increasingly important. Opportunity-centric policies could target improvements in neighborhoods, schools, or both. However, we lack a comprehensive framework to evaluate the relative effectiveness of these interventions or understand how changes in one context might impact the other. For instance, bussing programs can enhance educational opportunities without altering residential landscapes, though they may affect neighborhood desirability and property values. Conversely, inclusionary zoning can alter neighborhood demographics, potentially necessitating changes in school boundaries (Owens, 2017, p. 64).

Despite the evident interdependence of these critical contexts, we know little about their geographic overlap, the social interactions within them, or the policy frameworks that connect them. This paper introduces a research framework to explore these issues in detail, addressing three key questions: (1) How do school catchment zones align with the socioeconomic characteristics of the neighborhoods they serve? (2) Are school-aged populations more diverse within these catchment zones than in the broader neighborhood context? (3) How do segregation patterns across metropolitan areas relate to the spatial congruence between catchments and neighborhoods? Answering these questions offers a unique perspective on how segregation permeates multiple aspects of spatial structure.

Understanding the relationship between social contexts and outcomes such as educational attainment, health, and socioeconomic mobility has been a central focus of social science and policy research for decades. Extensive literature explores how "neighborhood effects," driven by residential locations, impact these outcomes over the life course, highlighting the role of racial, ethnic, and socioeconomic segregation in defining the "geography of opportunity" and reinforcing social inequality (DeLuca & Dayton, 2009; DeLuca & Rosenblatt, 2010; Reardon, Weathers, Fahle, Jang, & Kalogrides, 2019).

Similarly, research into educational environments examines how school segregation and resource disparities contribute to differences in achievement and economic mobility.

These questions are deeply intertwined, as residential location typically determines public school enrollment based on local district boundaries. Although private schooling and open enrollment policies complicate these relationships, the majority of students still attend their local public school (Owens, 2017).

Policy solutions aimed at creating equitable opportunities have shown promise at both ends of the spectrum. Greater access to high-quality schools can be facilitated through residential mobility, while redrawing school boundaries can help rectify entrenched segregation patterns (Wei, Feng, Rey, & Knaap, 2022). However, most research focuses on neighborhoods or schools in isolation, missing the dynamic relationship between residential sorting and the provision of public goods like education, a central tenet of urban economics and regional science (Tiebout, 1956). This oversight is notable given the profound impact of these zones on their inhabitants and how housing markets and location choices respond to perceptions of these areas.

Despite their importance, formal definitions of neighborhoods and the spatial relationships between neighborhoods and school catchment zones have received limited attention. Most research uses census units (tracts, block groups, blocks) as proxies for neighborhoods and examines demographic characteristics against a few school boundaries. While this approach provides insights into schools or neighborhoods, it does not reveal the dynamic interaction between these geographic contexts. This gap in understanding critical spatial contexts requires frameworks to disentangle the influences of school and neighborhood contexts (Rich & Owens, 2023).

This paper revisits the spatial school-neighborhood nexus and contributes four distinct methodological innovations to this literature. First, it introduces comprehensive, reproducible approaches for defining neighborhoods in research examining the school-neighborhood nexus. Second, it implements a measure of local spatial congruence for schools and neighborhoods, a concept first introduced two decades ago but not yet empirically applied (Galster, 2001). Third, it devises a novel measure of spatial entropy that captures local diversity within each geography, providing insights into the interrelationship between

neighborhoods and schools. This framework enables the exploration of potential feedback effects of policy interventions in both contexts (Rich & Owens, 2023).

Using data from the United States, we compute these measures for all school districts and neighborhoods within a nationally representative set of Core-Based Statistical Areas. We analyze the spatial and statistical relationships that emerge and examine how schools may influence, moderate, or exacerbate segregation in their communities. We conclude by discussing the framework’s general utility and potential extensions, providing a roadmap for future research focused on spatial spillovers between partially-nested geographies. These contributions respond to calls for scholarship that assesses the relationship between macro-level contextual effects and inequalities in outcomes, particularly examining the impact of residential and school segregation on educational disparities (Rich & Owens, 2023).

In the remainder of the paper, we first take a selective look at the literature on neighborhoods and schools, raising several methodological challenges that to date have received only limited attention. In section 3, we then introduce new methods for neighborhood delineation that improve upon the existing approaches that have supported spatial education research. We also develop new spatial analytics that express the concordance between school catchment zones and the socioeconomic neighborhoods in which those zones are embedded. Section 4 describes our research design of an empirical illustration involving 110 metropolitan areas to examine the school-neighborhood nexus. The results are reported in Section 5. We conclude in Section 6 with a discussion of the key findings and their implication for policy and future research.

2 Literature

Tieboutian Sorting and School Segregation

Schools are a key component of residential location choice, and studying the relationship between education systems and housing markets has been a central topic of study in urban economics, regional science, and public finance since the seminal contributions of Tiebout (1956). In his classic work, Tiebout described how residents choose public goods

like education systems by sorting into the municipalities that offer the tax bundle (e.g. education spending) that matches their preferences. A large body of work demonstrates that evidence for the Tiebout hypothesis is strong (people do tend to “vote with their feet”), but also that greater levels of Tieboutian sorting, such as places with increased municipal fragmentation can lead to increased segregation along dimensions of race and class (Banzhaf & Walsh, 2013; Dawkins, 2005; Dynarski, Schwab, & Zampelli, 1989; Heikkila, 1996).

Despite the large literature on Tieboutian sorting, one issue that is seldom raised is spatial scale. In its strictest form, Tiebout’s description of spatial equilibrium requires differing tax districts, which allow residents to pay for different education services according to their willingness. But similar sorting processes also operate at a hyper-local level *within* a municipality or jurisdiction, as residents select into the catchment boundaries of local schools (inside a given school district). Despite residing inside a single tax district, the quality of local schools (or perception thereof) can vary widely, and affects how residents choose and compete for homes to secure education services. This suggests that local school attendance boundaries may also reinforce multidimensional segregation at the neighborhood level, similar to the evidence of Tieboutian sorting at the municipal scale. The “clubbing” phenomenon has never been studied at this scale, though recent evidence in the education literature suggests that increased school choice options via new school openings (Taylor, Frankenberg, & Siegel-Hawley, 2019), charter schooling (Saporito, 2003), or open enrollment policy (Candipan, 2019) mirrors the increase in segregation commonly described in the residential sorting literature in urban economics.

In the case of highly localized Tieboutian sorting, a high congruence measure would indicate a process where similar groups are selecting into a school district (and possibly hoarding educational opportunity (Dawkins, 2023; Ellen, 2023; Galster, 2023)). For example, a body of work in urban economics examines whether municipalities form “Tieboutian clubs” where groups of similar people move into the same municipality to generate political control (resulting in greater multidimensional segregation). If the local neighborhood is defined in terms of race and class, then a high congruence measure in this context might

indicate “clubbing” behavior at the school level, as groups of parents coalesce to form homogeneous communities (Eberts & Gronberg, 1981).

Prior research has made clear the ways that neighborhood structure can have negative consequences for educational achievement in segregated communities (Quillian, 2014), and recent work reinforces the importance of integration in fostering economic mobility. In particular, Chetty et al. (2022) demonstrate the value of *bridging* social capital as more diverse networks provide a benefit for students from lower socioeconomic status strata without imposing any negative externalities on other strata (Putnam, 2001). This research suggests that when school attendance boundaries are drawn in ways that enhance the diversity of their student populations, they provide an aggregate benefit for students, whereas when they are drawn in ways that emphasize local segregation, they effectively provide a net welfare loss.

The issues of “freedom to sort into boundaries” also mirrors the conversation involving charter schooling and open enrollment policies, both of which provide increase avenues for school choice but may also exacerbate existing inequalities due to differences in the ability to “choose” (Saporito, 2003). Here we argue that building a bridge between the urban economics literature on location sorting and the education literature on school sorting may offer new and useful insight into the local politics of boundary delineation.

The debate on whether school attendance zones exacerbate or reflect residential segregation (Richards, 2014; Saporito & Sohoni, 2006) centers on the relationship between the geography of the catchment zones and the socioeconomic structure of the neighborhoods that the schools and catchment zones are embedded within. The residential sorting perspective is an important direction for the school boundary literature, which has often been focused on the delineation of school catchments as opposed to the sorting of residents into existing boundaries. To influence school equity in the latter scenario, land-use policies outside the education sphere would be most effective in fostering integration, so this dual perspective offers alternative paths for equitable public policy intervention.

However, as Owens, Reardon, and Jencks (2016, p. 1165) point out, there is “am-

biguity in how neighborhood, school, and district segregation relate to one another”. This is because the empirical analysis of this association requires a spatially explicit definition of neighborhood. Yet, despite the focused interest in the relationships between schools and neighborhoods, we suggest that the formal definition of neighborhoods has not been sufficiently examined.

Defining the “Neighborhood” in School-Centric Research

There have been multiple approaches to defining neighborhoods in the school and neighborhoods literature. Most common is the adoption of a given administrative unit, typically a census tract (Candipan & Brazil, 2020; Owens, 2012, 2020; Phillips, Koon, & Folch, 2020), census block group (Pearman, 2020), or zip code (Catsambis & Beveridge, 2001; Fruchter, Hester, Mokhtar, & Shahn, 2012), as equivalent to the neighborhood. Subsequently, many authors have used these operationalizations to argue that the interaction between neighborhoods and school catchment boundaries serve to exacerbate existing social inequalities, particularly through the maintenance of racial and socioeconomic segregation (Bernelius & Vilkkama, 2019; Reardon et al., 2019; Saporito & Van Riper, 2016)

The notion that administrative boundaries serve as good (or even adequate) approximations of social neighborhoods, however, has been challenged repeatedly in the literature. In a review of the neighborhood effects literature, Sampson, Morenoff, and Gannon-Rowley (2002, 470) advocate the use of more sophisticated methods in “redefining neighborhood boundaries in ways that are more consonant with social interactions and children’s experiences.” Grannis (2005, 296) argues that “using census-defined boundaries defines neighborhoods spatially but not socially” leading to an improper focus on geography at the expense of understanding the social networks and interactive processes that take place within communities. Instead, Grannis develops a method to identify neighborhoods using street network patterns, showing that social interactions are more frequent and communities are more homogeneous inside these smaller units articulated by urban infrastructure. More recently, Hipp and Boessen (2013) and Kim and Hipp (2020) expand this concept into the notion of

“egohoods”, a bespoke geography unique to each resident that extends outward from their place of residence along street networks. A slightly different framework is articulated by Galster (2001, 2019), who conceives “the neighborhood” not as a single entity, but rather as a set of overlapping and partially nested “externality spaces”, each of which may exert its own influence at a unique scope and scale. This model is largely consistent with classic concepts advanced by Suttles (1972) and more recently advocated by Petrović, Manley, and van Ham (2019).

One alternative to using census enumeration units as proxies for neighborhoods is to generate new neighborhood boundaries using Thiessen polygons that take a school as a generating point and partition the wider urban community into mutually exclusive and exhaustive zones such that each point within a given polygon has that generator school as its nearest school. This approach was used by Richards (2014) who then assigned community characteristics to the resulting polygons based on whether a census unit’s centroid was contained in the derived polygon. This approach is both conceptually and computationally simple, but also ignores the *actual* boundaries which define school attendance zones, as well as other considerations like school capacity, or physical barriers.

A different approach is to define a typology of neighborhoods through the use of a combination of principal components and cluster analysis applied to census or American Community Survey data (Brazil & Candipan, 2021; Candipan & Brazil, 2020; Owens, 2012, 2020). There have been slightly different variants of this approach. For example, Candipan and Brazil (2020) define the neighborhood typology using attendance zone boundaries after first having employed spatial interpolation of Census/ACS data to develop estimates for socioeconomic characteristics for the zones. Here the attendance zones are treated as neighborhoods in the subsequent analysis. While this, in part, acknowledges the previous criticisms with using census enumeration units as neighborhoods, this approach is not fully free of these issues. This is because the labeling of each census unit is a-spatial in the sense that the typology does not take spatial relationships into account. That is, the typology approach identifies *categories* of neighborhoods, regardless of where in the region they exist,

which eschews the notion that neighborhoods are spatially bounded.

Critiques of neighborhood constructs have not been ignored in the school nexus literature. In recent work, authors have begun to acknowledge and examine the uncertainty surrounding the scale of neighborhoods as they relate to school-based research questions. Pearman (2020) examines this issue through a sensitivity analysis of the relationship between neighborhood poverty and the effectiveness of preschool programs. Despite some recent fleeting attention, however, the vast majority of existing research views the spatial incongruence between neighborhoods and catchment zones as a problem to be addressed with various interpolation approaches. This effectively collapses neighborhoods and school catchment zones, which represent two distinct spatial externality spaces (Galster, 2001, 2019), into a single dimension. We concur with recent works (Brazil, 2016; Rich & Owens, 2023) which view the discordance between school and neighborhood geographies as potentially representing useful information. We argue that this should not be discarded but rather integrated into subsequent analyses, especially as investigations of the school-neighborhood nexus turn more and more to the ways that these geographic contexts mediate each other, as opposed to their direct effects on the life course. In this paper we offer a method for that integration.

In particular, we are interested in *congruence*, "the degree to which an individual's externality spaces correspond to particular, predetermined geographical boundaries" (Galster, 2019), and in this case, we examine congruence between socially-demarcated "neighborhoods" and administratively-defined school catchment boundaries. This question bears unique significance in the neighborhood effects literature because, unlike most other dimensions of the externality space, the school catchment zone has a large degree of political and policy control over how it is defined. That means it can be artificially bounded to enhance or diminish other potential influences of the externality space. That is, school boundaries can be drawn to help mitigate school-level segregation, e.g. by integrating the bounds of different racially-homogeneous zones.

3 Measuring the Spatial Structure of the School-Neighborhood Nexus

We suggest a new approach towards measuring the spatial structure of the school-neighborhood nexus. These consist of [1] defining neighborhoods using geodemographic methods; [2] formalizing spatially explicit measures of school-neighborhood congruence; and [3] finding the school diversity of neighborhoods, and the neighborhood diversity of schools. Apart from providing a more theoretically-grounded and methodologically-sound approach toward studying the relationship between schools and neighborhoods, this workflow also permits the investigation of the ways that schools can facilitate intergroup contact, providing “bridges” across different spatially-bounded social networks.

Measures of the School-Neighborhood Nexus

We formalize the school-neighborhood spatial nexus by drawing on topological measures applied to catchment zone and neighborhood polygons. Specifically, we use several spatial predicates defined on point set topology (Egenhofer & Franzosa, 1991). A *polygon*, a , is specified by designating three sets of points in the plane, interior points a^o , boundary points δa , and exterior points a^e . These three sets define a mutually exclusive and exhaustive partitioning of the plane.

Given a pair of polygons a and b so defined, polygon a *contains* polygon b if $b \cap a = b \wedge a^o \cap b^e \neq \emptyset$. a contains b implies that b is *within* a . Two polygons a and b *intersect* if $a^o \cap b^o \neq \emptyset$. Two polygons a and b *touch* if $\delta a \cap \delta b \neq \emptyset \wedge a^o \cap b^o = \emptyset$. Finally, the union of two polygons a and b is $a \cup b = a + b - a \cap b$.

Measures of Catchment Zone and Neighborhood Congruence. Congruence can be considered from the perspective of a catchment zone in terms of how tightly integrated that school is to the embedding neighborhoods.

Let C_s represent the polygon for catchment zone s , and N_i represent the polygon for neighborhood i . For each catchment zone C_s , we consider its spatial relations with the

neighborhoods it draws children from. More formally,

$$\Omega_s = \frac{|C_s \cap G_s|}{|C_s \cup G_s|} \quad (1)$$

where G_s is defined as:

$$G_s = \bigcup_{i \in \Gamma_s} N_i, \{i \in \Gamma_s \mid N_i \cap C_s \neq \emptyset\} \quad (2)$$

Ω_s from equation (1) provides an index of congruence for a catchment zone and the neighborhoods that it draws from. The numerator in (1) is the area of the intersection of C_s and G_s . G_s is the set of the neighborhoods that intersect C_s . The denominator is the area of the union of catchment zone C_s and all the neighborhoods that intersect C_s . Because the latter includes the area of each neighborhood within the catchment zone as well as any area of the union that is in the exterior to the catchment zone, it allows us to measure the congruence between the catchment zone and the set of neighborhoods that feed into that school. The maximum congruence is obtained with $\Omega_s = 1$, in which case the catchment zone is composed of a mutually exclusive and exhaustive subset of N , where N is the set of neighborhoods that themselves partition the metropolitan area into n mutually exclusive and exhaustive units. As Ω_s approaches 0, the catchment zone congruence with its embedding neighborhoods lessens.

We would find low congruence between the school boundary and the neighborhood in a case where the school boundary is designed to integrate multiple neighborhoods. Alternatively, a high congruence would indicate that the boundaries of neighborhoods and school catchments are largely in concert with one another and may help foster existing segregation patterns as the school's makeup will reflect the same demographics as the neighborhood in which it resides. Additionally, this measure has a dual perspective which turns the focus onto neighborhoods and the question of how a neighborhood interfaces with the catchment(s) it intersects, which may reveal new insights on the connection between schools and neighborhoods.

We illustrate this spatial congruence measure for the example shown in Figures 1 and 2

which contain the neighborhood and catchment boundaries, respectively, for a hypothetical area that contains 20 neighborhoods feeding 10 catchments.

Figure 1. Neighborhoods for a community.

Figure 3 shows the spatial distribution of the school to neighborhood congruence values. The Ω_s values range from a high of 0.56 for $s05$ to a low of 0.13 for $s09$. One way to interpret the school-neighborhood concordance value of 0.56 is that school $s05$ claims 56 percent of the area of the neighborhoods it intersects with.

School spatial neighborhood diversity. We also introduce a new measure to quantify the school-neighborhood nexus that we term *spatial neighborhood diversity* (SND) or spatial entropy, *sentropy*. Unlike the congruence measure described above, which captures the overlap between a school catchment boundary and the neighborhoods with which it intersects (as well as the converse: the overlap between a neighborhood and the catchment boundaries it intersects), the SND metric captures the neighborhood diversity embodied by a school catchment zone (or the school diversity embodied by a neighborhood). That is, it measures the extent to which a school boundary draws students from multiple

Figure 2. Catchments for a community.

neighborhoods. Since our definition of “neighborhood” is based, in part, on demographic homogeneity, the SND captures a school’s integrative capacity.

We define this as follows:

$$entropy_s = -1 \sum_{i \in \Gamma_s} w_{i,s} \log(w_{i,s}) \quad (3)$$

with:

$$w_{i,s} = \frac{|N_i \cap C_s|}{\sum_{i \in \Gamma_s} |N_i \cap C_s|} \quad (4)$$

The spatial (neighborhood) diversity of a school will grow with [1] the number of neighborhoods it intersects, and [2] the distribution of the shares of the union intersection each neighborhood represents. When a school draws students from multiple neighborhoods, SND increases in value, although there is no theoretical maximum value. When the SND measure is zero, it suggests a Tieboutian clubbing process where social boundaries are in perfect concert with the school attendance zone. When a catchment serves only a single

Figure 3. School spatial congruence. School catchments are labeled with sx with black boundaries. Neighborhoods are labeled with hx with white boundaries.

neighborhood, $entropy_s = 0$, and we refer to the catchment as a *neighborhood homogeneous school*. Figure 4 contains the school spatial diversity for the 10 catchments. $s01$ is the school with the lowest spatial diversity, as it intersects three neighborhoods ($h09, h05, h14$) with $h09$ accounting for the largest share of the intersection, and $h14$ a tiny fraction. The most neighborhood diverse catchment is $s05$ which draws from 7 neighborhoods.

Neighborhood to School Congruence. We can also measure the congruence from the perspective of a neighborhood unit.

$$\Omega_i = \frac{|N_i \cap G_i|}{|N_i \cup G_i|} \quad (5)$$

where G_i is defined as:

$$G_i = \bigcup_{s \in \Gamma_i} C_s, \{s \in \Gamma_i \mid C_s \cap N_i \neq \emptyset\} \quad (6)$$

Here the numerator is the area of the intersection of a neighborhood and the union

Figure 4. School spatial diversity. School catchments are labeled with sx with black boundaries. Neighborhoods are labeled with hx with white boundaries.

of catchment zones that draw from the neighborhood. The denominator is the area of the union of the neighborhood and the catchment zones drawing from that neighborhood.

The neighborhood to school congruence measure tells us how dominant this particular neighborhood is relative to the catchment zone(s) it contributes to. As the value goes to 1, a larger share of the students at the involved school(s) will be from this particular neighborhood. In other words, less neighborhood mixing happens at these schools. Conversely, as the neighborhood-congruence measure goes towards 0, students from this neighborhood represent a smaller share of attendance at the involved schools.

In Figure 5, the maximum neighborhood-school congruence value is found in neighborhood $h09$ with $\Omega_9 = 0.42$. The weakest neighborhood-school congruence is in neighborhood $h08$ with $\Omega_8 = 0.07$.

Neighborhood spatial school diversity. We can also measure the spatial diversity of neighborhoods. More specifically, we consider the spatial (school) diversity of a

Figure 5. Neighborhood (hx) spatial congruence boundaries (white), school (hx) boundaries (black).

neighborhood, or the neighborhood's spatial entropy, as:

$$entropy_h = -1 \sum_{s \in \Gamma_h} w_{h,s} \log(w_{h,s}) \quad (7)$$

with:

$$w_{h,s} = \frac{|N_h \cap C_s|}{\sum_{s \in \Gamma_h} |N_h \cap C_s|} \quad (8)$$

When a neighborhood intersects only a single catchment, the neighborhood is said to be *school homogeneous*. The spatial school diversity of the different neighborhoods is shown in Figure 6. There are five neighborhoods that are school homogeneous ($h3, h4, h11, h12, h19$), with spatial entropy values of 0. The most school diverse neighborhoods are $h6$ and $h7$ with spatial entropy values of 1.12 and 1.02, respectively.

School to Neighborhood Congruence and Neighborhood to School Congruence. Together, these statistics provide unique insight into the ways that schools

Figure 6. Neighborhood spatial diversity. School catchments are labeled with sx with black boundaries. Neighborhoods are labeled with hx with white boundaries.

contribute to the prevailing patterns of integration or segregation in their greater communities. The socioeconomic and ethnoracial mixing that an individual student will experience will be a function of both types of congruence measures. If a student lives in a spatially diverse neighborhood, their neighborhood feeds multiple catchment zones. A student living in a such a neighborhood has a higher probability of forming ties with neighbors attending different schools than if they lived in a less spatially diverse neighborhood. The other dimension to consider is the spatial diversity of the school that a student attends. Students at a spatially diverse school have a higher probability of interacting with students from different neighborhoods at school, than do students at a school with a low measure of spatial diversity.

Additional spatial measures of schools and neighborhoods. In addition to the measures above, we also develop several measures of the spatial characteristics of both catchment zones and schools. *Spatial Centrality:* As a measure of spatial centrality we

consider the relative distance a school or neighborhood is from the weighted mean population center of the community. The latter is defined using the centroids of the unit weighted by population. The spatial centrality of a unit j is given as:

$$sc_j = 1 - \frac{d_{j,c} - \min(d_{.,c})}{\max(d_{.,c}) - \min(d_{.,c})} \quad (9)$$

where $d_{j,c}$ is the distance between unit j and the community centroid at c .¹ *Shape*: Given the debate about whether catchment's have been gerrymandered or not (i.e., Richards, 2014; Saporito & Van Riper, 2016), we develop a measure of shape for each catchment as well as neighborhood. We adopt a circularity measure which is the ratio of the area of a shape to the area of a circle whose circumference equals the perimeter of the shape:

$$CR_j = \frac{4\Pi A_j}{P_j^2} \quad (10)$$

where A_j is the area of unit j and P_j is the shape's perimeter. As the circularity ratio approaches unity, the shape becomes more circular.² We include the unit's population *density* (population/km2) and *area* (km2) as additional spatial characteristics.

We also implement multiple measures of the ethnoracial characteristics of catchments and neighborhoods. A measure of *relative diversity* is adopted from Saporito and Van Riper (2016):

$$\text{Relative Diversity}_j = 1 - .5 \left(\sum_{k=1}^K |\pi_k - \pi_{j,k}| \right) \quad (11)$$

where $\pi_{j,k}$ is the proportion of unit j 's population in group k , and π_k is the proportion of the metropolitan region's population in that group. Neighborhoods or catchments whose composition identically match that of the metro will have values of one for the relative diversity measure. In addition to relative diversity, we calculate the ethnoracial entropy of each unit:

¹The centroid of the neighborhood or catchment is used to measure $d_{j,c}$.

²For an overview of measures of shape in gerrymandering forensics see Wolf (2017).

$$\text{Entropy}_j = -1 \sum_{k=1}^k \pi_{j,k} \log(\pi_{j,k}) . \quad (12)$$

4 The school-neighborhood nexus in the United States

We apply the methods from Section 3 to a case study of large metropolitan areas in the United States.

Data

To understand the relationship between neighborhoods and school catchments we use data from the 2014-2018 American Community Survey (ACS) 5-year estimates, published by U.S. Census Bureau, and the 2015-2016 School Attendance Boundary Survey (SABS), published by the National Center for Educational Statistics³. Our neighborhoods are constructed from census tract data in the 2020 Core-Based Statistical Area boundaries (CBSA) with a total population greater than 500,000 (n=110). Summary statistics for these CBSAs are contained in Table A1.⁴

Defining Neighborhoods. Defining “neighborhoods” for social scientific work is a contentious process. For the purpose of the present study, the perfect operationalization of neighborhood is not necessary. Given our interest in multidimensional segregation and residential sorting, our notion of neighborhood is simply a spatially distinct zone that is roughly homogeneous along a set of sociodemographic indicators. To identify these zones, we draw on recent advances in geodemographics, by applying spatially constrained clustering algorithms to define socioeconomic neighborhoods in each of the region under investigation. These algorithms work by grouping together contiguous collections of spatial units (census tracts, in this case) that are similar along a set of input variables. This automates a process similar to that used by Sampson, Raudenbush, and Earls (1997) to study “neighborhood clusters” in Chicago.

³In subsequent use we adopt the acronym “SABs” in reference to school attendance boundaries

⁴We adopt census tracts as our enumeration units due to the wider scope of socioeconomic variables available at that level to facilitate neighborhood delineation and our subsequent analysis.

We use the *max-p regions* algorithm from the `pysal-spoint` module (Gaboardi, Rey, Knaap, Feng, & Wei, 2021) which does not impose a prior definition of the number of neighborhoods in the clustering process, but rather endogenizes this number (Wei, Rey, & Knaap, 2021). Instead, the algorithm relies on a threshold variable, which sets a floor that all neighborhoods must respect. That is, instead of identifying an arbitrary constant number of neighborhoods in each metro region, we say that a neighborhood must contain at least 8000 people (again, corresponding to the process used by Sampson et al. (1997, p. 919)), and be as similar as possible along the input dimensions, but the number of neighborhoods in each metropolitan region is variable. The specific ACS variables used in the regionalization are: Percent Non-Hispanic White persons, Percent Non-Hispanic Black persons, Percent Asian persons, Percent Hispanic persons, Percent female-headed families, Percent of the population 25 years or older with Bachelor’s degree or greater, Percent poverty rate, Number total population, Number households, Number persons under 18 years old, Number persons over 60 years old, Median household income, Median home value, and Median contract rent.

The algorithm creates spatially-bounded “neighborhoods,” such that internal homogeneity is maximized along dimensions of race and socioeconomic status, but each neighborhood remains unique and geographically distinct. This process is largely consistent with longstanding neighborhood designations in cities such as Chicago or Pittsburgh, where official neighborhood definitions have been in place for nearly a century. In these examples, neighborhood delineations were based on both demographic composition as well as geographic location, yielding distinct boundaries and nomenclature such as “Ukrainian Village”, “Little Italy”, or “Polish Hill”(Clark, 2021).⁵ For the remainder of the paper, we refer to these socially-homogeneous zones as “neighborhoods”

School Attendance Boundaries. We assign catchments to the CBSA that contains the catchment centroid. We then subset these SABs to include only SABs which contain first grade (primary schools). We also remove all SABs with open enrollment poli-

⁵The max-p algorithm has been applied elsewhere to examine spatial dynamics and neighborhood change (Rey et al., 2011).

cies, and removed some unassigned polygons from the remaining SABs.⁶

Spatial Interpolation. Having defined the geodemographic neighborhoods and selected catchment zones, we then use `pysal-tobler` (Knaap et al., 2021) to interpolate the ACS variables to these neighborhoods and catchments. In addition to the socioeconomic variables used to define the neighborhoods, we also estimate the number and proportion of the population under 15 years old for the following groups for each of the neighborhoods and catchment zones: Non-Hispanic White, Non-Hispanic Black, Hispanic, and Asian. This will allow us to consider segregation and diversity differences between the aggregate and school-age populations.

Spatial Scale

We apply the measures from Section 3 to analyze the school-neighborhood nexus at two spatial scales: school/neighborhood, and metropolitan region. At the level of the individual neighborhood or school we examine several dimensions. First, we explore the distribution of congruence values for both the neighborhoods and schools to gain insights into the properties of these measures. We then examine a series of correlates measured at the same scale, including the diversity of the population in a given unit as well as the centrality or spatial context of the unit, and measures of the shape of the unit. Finally, at the metropolitan scale, we extend the investigation of the relationships between school-neighborhood congruence and segregation.

Our resulting sample includes the 110 CBSAs summarized in Table 1. These range in size from New York-Newark-Jersey-City CBSA with a population of 19 million down to the Santa Rosa-Petaluma, CA CBSA with a population just over 500 thousand. The median CBSA has 981 thousand population and is 65 percent Non-Hispanic White. There is a wide range in diversity from the Portland-South Portland Maine CBSA which is 92.2 percent Non-Hispanic White to McAllen-Edinburg-Mission, Texas which is 6.3 percent Non-Hispanic

⁶There are also cases where multiple school names are associated with the same catchment. This is due to different grade level schools occupying the same location. In these cases, we retain one catchment record and drop the duplicate records.

White, while three-quarters of the CBSAs are majority Non-Hispanic White. Together these 110 CBSAs contain 24,507 elementary school catchments and 17,608 geodemographic neighborhoods.

	Neighborhoods	Primary Catchments	Population (1,000)	Non-Hispanic White %
count	17608	24507	220763	
mean	160	223	20072	62.4
std	209	280	2620	17.4
min	34	45	501	6.3
25%	55	80	677	52.1
50%	77	118	981	65.9
75%	184	240	2179	76.0
max	1506	1867	19318	92.2

Table 1

Summary statistics for the 110 Core Based Statistical Areas.

5 Results

School and Neighborhood Scale

School-Neighborhood Congruence. We begin with a comparison of the spatial characteristics of school catchment zones and neighborhoods for the complete sample of 110 metropolitan areas. Figure 7a displays the densities for the values of Ω from equations (1) and (5) for both the neighborhoods and school catchments for our sample. Both distributions are right-skewed but display different peaks as neighborhoods are bimodal with a first peak close to 0 and a second out at 0.20 with a median of 0.25. In contrast, school catchment zones have a median Ω of 0.20. Thus, at the medians, neighborhoods have higher congruence with the school catchment zones that they contribute to, when compared to the congruence that catchments have with the neighborhoods they draw from.

The size distributions of the two sets of units are also distinct as show in Figure 7b. Neighborhoods tend to be larger than catchments, which reflects schools outnumbering neighborhoods. The shape distributions are also different across the neighborhoods and schools Figure 7c. On average, catchments are more circular in shape than neighborhoods, although the catchment distribution has a fatter lower tail indicating the presence of catchments that are irregularly shaped.

Figure 7. Spatial attributes of catchments and neighborhoods

The spatial entropy (diversity) distributions are markedly different between the neighborhoods and schools, with neighborhoods displaying higher spatial entropy (Figure 7d). Neighborhoods intersect with catchments in a more spatially diverse fashion than what holds for the way that catchments intersect with neighborhoods. The take-away here is that these units are not identical in their spatial structure.

Moving to pairwise associations of these spatial attributes, Figure 8 summarizes the correlations between the spatial characteristics for the catchments. Catchments with more central locations in their metropolitan areas have higher density. Density and circularity are also positively related. More central catchments also display higher spatial entropy. The congruence of catchments is weakly associated with most of the other spatial attributes, positively so with size, circularity, and negatively with centrality, density and spatial entropy.

The negative association between congruence and spatial entropy suggests the two measures are capturing different components of a school's spatial relationship to the neighborhoods it serves. Figure 9 reports the same pairwise association between spatial attributes but this time for the neighborhoods - in general terms, similar patterns to those seen for catchments are repeated. At the same time, the negative association between neighborhood congruence and spatial entropy is stronger than was the case for catchments.

Figure 8. Correlations between catchment spatial attributes.

Race and Space. Shifting the focus to the relationships between ethnoracial composition and the spatial characteristics of the catchments in Figure 10, several contrasts emerge. As expected, as the proportion of Asian, Hispanic, or Black population in a catchment grows, the ethnoracial diversity (**entropy**) increases, while diversity declines with increases in the proportion of the catchment that is Non-Hispanic White.

The second result of note is the difference in the sign of the association between spatial entropy and composition for Blacks and Whites. This reveals that as the Black proportion of a catchment grows, the catchment is pulling from a greater number of neighborhoods, while

Figure 9. Correlations between neighborhood spatial attributes.

for the Non-Hispanic White proportion the correlation moves in the opposite direction. The same difference holds for Hispanic and Whites, as well as Asian and Non-Hispanic Whites, although with weaker correlations. There is also profound separation of Non-Hispanic Whites and Hispanics, and Non-Hispanic Whites and Blacks across catchments reflected in very strong negative correlations in their respective proportions of catchment populations.

Another difference along ethnoracial groups concerns the shape of catchments. The circularity of catchments is positively correlated with the Black, Hispanic, and Asian proportions of catchment population, while the association is negative for the Non-Hispanic White proportion. Related to this, as the spatial diversity of catchments increases, the catchments become less circular. In other words, catchments that pull from multiple neighborhoods tend to have less regular shapes. There is also a positive association between the spatial diversity of a catchment and the catchment's ethnoracial diversity, as catchments that pull from more neighborhoods (and do so in an even fashion) have higher ethnoracial diversity.

Like Saporito and Van Riper (2016), we find that as the relative diversity of a catchment increases the shape of the catchment becomes less regular (circular). However, we find a positive association between the ethnoracial entropy of a catchment and the circularity of the catchment shape.

When we consider the school-aged populations in the catchments in Figure 11, we find, in general, similar associations between measures of ethnoracial and spatial dimensions of the catchments. The exceptions pertain to the circularity of the catchments and diversity, which have a positive association for the general population but weakly negative for the school-aged population. At the same time, the negative association between relative diversity and circularity of the catchment also holds for the school-aged population. We also find a positive association between relative diversity and the spatial entropy of catchments, both for the overall population and the school-aged population.

Figure 10. Correlations between catchment ethnoracial and spatial attributes for total population

Figure 12 explores the relationship between school-aged diversity and total diversity by catchment. The figure plots the entropy for the total population (x-axis) and school-aged population (y-axis) for each catchment, together with a LOESS curve, and the line of equality. One clear pattern that emerges is that the entropy increases for the school-aged

Figure 11. Correlations between catchment ethnoracial and spatial attributes for school-aged population

populations relative to the catchment population when the proportion of Non-Hispanic White in the school aged population grows. This suggests that the catchment boundaries are drawn in such a way as to increase ethnoracial diversity for the school-aged populations, particularly in catchments that have low diversity to begin with.

Is segregation reduced by catchment boundaries?

At the metropolitan scale, we examine the relationship between segregation measured across the catchments versus segregation measured across the geodemographic neighborhoods. We use two different segregation indices, the multigroup dissimilarity index and the multigroup information theory index (Reardon & Firebaugh, 2002) using the `pysal-segregation` package (Cortes, Rey, Knaap, & Wolf, 2019). Figures 13(a) and 13(b) summarize these associations. For both indices, the level of segregation across the catchments (y-axis) tends to be lower than the segregation measured across the neighborhoods (x-axis) as the vast majority of cities fall below the 45-degree lines. This result is particularly striking when considering that the number of catchments generally exceeds the

Figure 12. Catchment ethnoraacial entropy for school-aged and total population.

number of neighborhoods in the metropolitan areas (and that, on average, catchments are smaller in area than neighborhoods), and in general terms as the number of spatial units grows the expectation is for the measure of segregation to also increase (Johnston, Manley, & Jones, 2018).

Neighborhood Congruence: Schools versus Districts

While the congruence between neighborhoods and school catchment zones has been our main focus, the question of the congruence between neighborhoods and districts requires consideration.⁷ Based on boundary discontinuity research (Gibbons, Machin, & Silva, 2013), school districts can often result in sharp lines that separate neighborhoods. Such a finding is consistent with the research demonstrating that segregation in the US has been increasing between districts, while decreasing within districts (Owens et al., 2016).

⁷We thank an anonymous reviewer for raising this issue.

Figure 13. School catchment segregation versus geodemographic neighborhood segregation by metropolitan region.

We repeat the analysis of neighborhood congruence for each CBSA, however, rather than measuring congruence between the neighborhood boundaries and the catchment boundaries in each metropolitan area, we measure the congruence between neighborhoods and district boundaries. The results are summarized in Figure 14.

There is a strong positive association in the levels of congruence between neighborhoods and educational boundaries across cities, whether those boundaries are for individual catchments or districts ($\rho = 0.75$). In other words, cities where neighborhoods have high (low) congruence with catchment boundaries also contain neighborhoods having high (low) congruence with district boundaries. We also find that neighborhood congruence with districts is higher than neighborhood congruence with catchments. In our sample, the median city has 35.6% of its neighborhoods spanning a district boundary, with a small number of cities (5) having all of their neighborhoods contained in a single district, and the maximum amount of splitting occurring in Santa Rosa-Petaluma, CA where districts split 73.3% of the neighborhoods.

Figure 14. Neighborhood congruence measured with catchments and districts by CBSA. The dotted line represents equality between the two congruence measures.

6 Discussion and Conclusion

The congruence and spatial diversity measures introduced in this paper provide a new look at the interaction between the abstract spaces that help define urban life. Although the measures are generic and applicable to any two externality spaces, the relationship between school attendance boundaries and socially-demarcated “neighborhoods” is of particular interest. From a sorting perspective, the congruence between these two zones suggests a highly localized Tieboutian residential selection process, whereas from an administrative process, high congruence could suggest educationally gerrymandered catchment zones. Absent temporal data it is impossible to disentangle the issues of sorting and boundary-editing, but both perspectives speak to the political economy of public school systems.

Our analysis of the largest 110 metropolitan regions in the United States reveals

complex but important findings about the spatial relationship between schools and neighborhoods, with consequential implications for students who inhabit each geographic zone. Congruence between schools and neighborhoods is the exception not the rule. Most catchments split multiple neighborhoods, and most neighborhoods feed multiple catchments. We find that school catchment boundaries become more irregularly-shaped when they draw from a larger set of discrete neighborhoods. As expected, since our definition of “neighborhood” is based on internal homogeneity, this increase in *spatial neighborhood diversity* results in greater ethnoracial integration at the school level. Put differently, when catchments have more irregular shapes, they tend to create more diverse environments for the students who attend the school. This finding lends support to work by Saporito and Van Riper (2016) who find, similarly, that irregular boundaries lead to more diversity. Using more stylized language, we interpret this finding to suggest that, on average, when school boundaries appear to be “gerrymandered,” the result is *greater* diversity, more often than less diversity. This does not suggest that school boundaries are necessarily drawn with the intent to integrate diverse students groups, or that certain boundaries may not be drawn for explicitly racist purposes (Monarrez & Chien, 2021). It does suggest, however, that the picture is complex.

We also find that when catchments tend to be centrally-located inside their respective metropolitan region, they also tend to be more circular, and draw from a set of neighborhoods whose student population is more diverse at the outset. The more central catchments also tend to be smaller, and are less likely to fully-contain any single neighborhood. From the alternative perspective, this means that catchments on the periphery of a metropolitan region tend to be larger and are more likely to contain a neighborhood fully. This finding suggests that in outlying suburban schools, students are more likely to attend the same school as everyone else in their neighborhood. Since outlying neighborhoods are less diverse to begin with, and we have demonstrated that greater neighborhood diversity at the school level leads to greater ethnoracial integration at the school, this finding may suggest that students in outlying schools are exposed to strongly racially-insular environments.

This result also speaks to the need for additional research that examines the role of spatial scale and intra-metropolitan variation in education systems. In the case of competitive urban/suburban dynamics, outlying schools are also more likely to reside in their own municipality (and tax district) which may exacerbate intra-metropolitan inequality (Katz & Gore, 2001; Rusk, 1993, 2010).

At the metropolitan scale, we find that school-age populations are more segregated across geodemographic neighborhoods compared the segregation across elementary school catchment zones. This finding is robust to the index of segregation adopted, and suggests that the drawing of school catchment boundaries has worked to reduce segregation at schools relative to that experienced in neighborhoods. Our results also point towards the mechanisms by which this reduction occurs, as metropolitan areas with higher levels of spatial entropy in their catchments have lower levels of segregation. Additionally, areas with catchments that have high spatial congruence with geodemographic neighborhoods have higher levels of segregation. In general terms, higher congruence implies that catchment boundaries reinforce neighborhood segregation in metropolitan areas.

An important distinction to bear in mind when interpreting these congruence measures is that school catchments and neighborhoods differ in the extent to which they are malleable through policy interventions. The boundaries of catchments can and are redrawn at the discretion of school districts, while the boundaries of neighborhoods are endogenous outcomes of neighborhood selection and sorting processes. In this regard, the dynamics of neighborhoods reflect not only compositional change but also spatial change (Rey et al., 2011), and this can complicate the analysis of neighborhood or school segregation dynamics impacts on educational outcomes (Goldsmith, 2009).

Given that the congruence measures are spatially explicit, local government and school analysts can utilize the congruence scores to inform geographically targeted policy interventions. By employing Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and other spatial data tools, they can visualize and analyze patterns of student demographics, performance metrics, and resource allocation across different neighborhoods. This spatial perspective allows them to

identify areas with significant disparities in educational resources, academic achievements, and socio-economic conditions. For instance, they can pinpoint schools that are underserved or isolated due to socio-economic or racial segregation and assess the impact of geographical factors like proximity to quality educational facilities or public transport. Armed with these insights, policymakers can design targeted interventions, such as redistributing resources, modifying school zoning policies, or implementing community support programs, to promote equity and enhance educational outcomes for all students. This approach ensures that policy decisions are data-driven and tailored to the specific needs and challenges of diverse communities within the school district.

While the congruence and spatial diversity measures we introduce in this paper provide new insight into the school-neighborhood nexus, there are also important qualifications to consider. First, school catchment data are imperfect and change over time. Although our time periods are consistent for matching across datasets in the analysis at hand, the relationships we discuss here are not static. Further, the catchment boundaries themselves may be worthy of additional research to understand the ways that open enrollment, private schooling, or overlapping catchment boundaries affect our understanding of these relationships. In our present work, we exclude open enrollment and private schools, and ignore planar enforcement, as it poses no mathematical issues for our statistical measures, but future work could explore these issues in depth. We also stress that our results are based on analyses of residential data, and not enrollment data.

Finally, while we have made theoretically justified choices to select our definition of “neighborhoods,” there are other potential operationalizations to consider. We adopt the max-p algorithm to define our neighborhoods because of its unique ability to define the number of neighborhoods endogenously, but there are also other regionalization methods to explore, other variables for defining neighborhoods, and other population thresholds to consider, all of which could be used to examine the robustness of our findings. Furthermore, because the max-p algorithm is stochastic in nature, it is also possible to leverage computational statistics to develop an inferential framework to examine, for example, the

empirical likelihood of obtaining our results at random.

It may also be possible to exploit time-series data on school attendance boundary changes to examine whether these changes lead to a new residential layout, or whether boundaries change in response to shifting residential patterns as suggested by Candipan (2019). With these more detailed data, additional research should proceed to analyze the multiple and interacting dimensions of “school choice,” which often means *neighborhood choice* Rich and Owens (2023). Local funding schemes, interplay between local and regional government schemes, and education policies like charter schooling, open enrollment, and private schooling all complicate these issues, but the measures of spatial interaction between school and “neighborhood contexts” we develop in this paper can help shed light on these dynamics. This is particularly true when they can be combined with local data and knowledge about particular education systems and their political economy.

Indeed, we believe that a critical avenue for further research is examining the sequencing of the relationship between boundary changes and demographic shifts. While this area is a growing research focus, the majority of empirical work adopts the lens of “gerrymandering,” or the notion that school boundaries are actively re-drawn in response to changes in the local demographic makeup. As the literature on residential location choice makes clear, however, the relationship between perceived school quality and neighborhood selection is complex and understanding the (in)congruence between neighborhoods and school—particularly in a temporal context—can help shed light on whether households respond to schools (as the urban economic literature suggests) or schools respond to households (as the education literature suggests). Furthermore, the congruence measures developed in this paper can be used as instruments to study multi-dimensional interaction patterns between schools and neighborhoods. In this sense, schools serve as a mechanism for behaviors, attitudes, or beliefs to be transmitted between neighborhoods *through* students who attend the same schools (despite residing in different neighborhoods). The congruence measures developed here could help conceptualize the strength of these potential pathways.

Following from this work, there are several avenues ripe for further research. First,

with the release of new data resources such as the Stanford Educational Opportunity Monitoring Project (Reardon et al., 2019), future work can examine the relationships between spatial congruence of schools and measures of educational outcomes. The bridge between school segregation and neighborhood segregation, and its associated effects on life outcomes (Chetty et al., 2022) can be examined through the lens of the new measures we develop here. The measures here could also be applied at the scale of school districts, as results from Saporito and Sohoni (2006) and Owens et al. (2016) suggest segregation has increased between districts while decreasing within districts. The extent to which school-neighborhood spatial congruence patterns vary across districts may shed light on the relationship between boundaries and segregation.

While our results suggest that catchment zones generally work to reduce segregation for school-aged populations, the question of whether further reductions in segregation are possible remains open. A recent application of a new location allocation model has shown the potential for reducing segregation in two large school districts in California (Wei et al., 2022). Enhancing that formulation to include the information in our new spatially explicit measures of the school-neighborhood nexus is a promising direction.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors have no conflicts of interest to report. The research relies on secondary data and, as such, informed consent is not applicable.

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Appendix

Table A1
Core Based Statistical Areas

CBSA	Name	State	Population (1000)	Non-Hispanic White %	Neighborhoods	Primary Catchments
10420	Akron	OH	704	80	65	77
10580	Albany-Schenectady-Troy	NY	880	80	69	97
10740	Albuquerque	NM	910	39	79	118
10900	Allentown-Bethlehem-Easton	PA	834	73	73	108
12060	Atlanta-Sandy Springs-Alpharetta	GA	5779	47	467	615
12260	Augusta-Richmond County	GA	594	54	40	61
12420	Austin-Round Rock-Georgetown	TX	2058	52	115	155
12540	Bakersfield	CA	883	34	73	136
12580	Baltimore-Columbia-Towson	MD	2793	57	247	395
12940	Baton Rouge	LA	852	57	61	66
13820	Birmingham-Hoover	AL	1082	62	87	96
14260	Boise City	ID	693	80	52	111
14460	Boston-Cambridge-Newton	MA	4811	70	228	336
14860	Bridgeport-Stamford-Norwalk	CT	944	62	66	96
15380	Buffalo-Cheektowaga	NY	1131	77	75	72
15980	Cape Coral-Fort Myers	FL	718	67	63	48
16700	Charleston-North Charleston	SC	759	64	65	81
16740	Charlotte-Concord-Gastonia	NC	2498	61	207	263
16860	Chattanooga	TN	552	78	45	63
16980	Chicago-Naperville-Elgin	IL	9536	53	810	1349
17140	Cincinnati	OH	2191	79	183	220
17460	Cleveland-Elyria	OH	2061	70	152	161
17820	Colorado Springs	CO	712	70	54	84
17900	Columbia	SC	816	56	73	111
18140	Columbus	OH	2054	73	174	249
19100	Dallas-Fort Worth-Arlington	TX	7189	46	510	804
19430	Dayton-Kettering	OH	802	76	73	89
19660	Deltona-Daytona Beach-Ormond Beach	FL	634	72	55	51
19740	Denver-Aurora-Lakewood	CO	2850	64	247	392
19780	Des Moines-West Des Moines	IA	671	81	60	110
19820	Detroit-Warren-Dearborn	MI	4317	66	314	378
20500	Durham-Chapel Hill	NC	617	54	49	58
21340	El Paso	TX	841	12	72	142
22180	Fayetteville	NC	515	48	44	76
22220	Fayetteville-Springdale-Rogers	AR	503	73	39	53
23420	Fresno	CA	978	29	89	179
24340	Grand Rapids-Kentwood	MI	1054	78	83	107
24660	Greensboro-High Point	NC	757	58	69	104
24860	Greenville-Anderson	SC	883	72	37	49
25420	Harrisburg-Carlisle	PA	567	77	42	58
25540	Hartford-East Hartford-Middletown	CT	1209	67	102	169
26420	Houston-The Woodlands-Sugar Land	TX	6779	36	520	741
26900	Indianapolis-Carmel-Anderson	IN	2007	72	164	243
27140	Jackson	MS	598	45	50	79
27260	Jacksonville	FL	1475	63	114	152
28140	Kansas City	MO	2106	72	185	374

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Table A1 – Continued from previous page

CBSA	Name	State	Population	Non-Hispanic	Neighborhoods	Primary
			(1000)	White %		Catchments
28940	Knoxville	TN	845	86	71	91
29460	Lakeland-Winter Haven	FL	668	59	59	60
29540	Lancaster	PA	538	82	48	66
29620	Lansing-East Lansing	MI	545	78	49	53
29820	Las Vegas-Henderson-Paradise	NV	2141	43	188	208
30460	Lexington-Fayette	KY	506	77	43	57
30780	Little Rock-North Little Rock-Conway	AR	734	67	64	100
31080	Los Angeles-Long Beach-Anaheim	CA	13262	29	1112	1450
31140	Louisville/Jefferson County	KY	1252	76	110	145
31540	Madison	WI	647	82	56	84
32580	McAllen-Edinburg-Mission	TX	849	6	71	168
32820	Memphis	TN	1337	43	34	45
33100	Miami-Fort Lauderdale-Pompano Beach	FL	6070	30	506	454
33340	Milwaukee-Waukesha	WI	1575	66	94	133
33460	Minneapolis-St. Paul-Bloomington	MN	3542	76	308	390
33700	Modesto	CA	539	42	44	80
34980	Nashville-Davidson-Murfreesboro-Franklin	TN	1839	72	158	216
35300	New Haven-Milford	CT	859	63	50	77
35380	New Orleans-Metairie	LA	1263	51	76	103
35620	New York-Newark-Jersey City	NY	19318	46	1506	1867
35840	North Port-Sarasota-Bradenton	FL	785	77	68	55
36260	Ogden-Clearfield	UT	652	81	56	118
36420	Oklahoma City	OK	1369	64	122	230
36540	Omaha-Council Bluffs	NE	922	76	83	173
36740	Orlando-Kissimmee-Sanford	FL	2450	47	187	215
37100	Oxnard-Thousand Oaks-Ventura	CA	848	45	74	121
37340	Palm Bay-Melbourne-Titusville	FL	576	74	51	52
37980	Philadelphia-Camden-Wilmington	PA	6069	62	502	663
38060	Phoenix-Mesa-Chandler	AZ	4673	55	393	521
38300	Pittsburgh	PA	2339	85	199	236
38860	Portland-South Portland	ME	529	92	42	69
38900	Portland-Vancouver-Hillsboro	OR	2417	73	210	317
39100	Poughkeepsie-Newburgh-Middletown	NY	672	67	48	53
39300	Providence-Warwick	RI	1615	75	94	143
39340	Provo-Orem	UT	601	82	54	99
39580	Raleigh-Cary	NC	1302	61	108	137
40060	Richmond	VA	1258	57	107	153
40140	Riverside-San Bernardino-Ontario	CA	4518	32	373	577
40380	Rochester	NY	1074	76	89	99
40900	Sacramento-Roseville-Folsom	CA	2291	52	196	300
41620	Salt Lake City	UT	1185	72	98	176
41700	San Antonio-New Braunfels	TX	2426	33	166	242
41740	San Diego-Chula Vista-Carlsbad	CA	3302	45	271	365
41860	San Francisco-Oakland-Berkeley	CA	4673	39	352	453
41940	San Jose-Sunnyvale-Santa Clara	CA	1981	32	140	173
42220	Santa Rosa-Petaluma	CA	501	63	46	65
42540	Scranton-Wilkes-Barre	PA	556	84	53	64
42660	Seattle-Tacoma-Bellevue	WA	3809	64	318	481
44060	Spokane-Spokane Valley	WA	542	85	49	87
44140	Springfield	MA	701	70	53	92

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Table A1 – *Continued from previous page*

CBSA	Name	State	Population	Non-Hispanic	Neighborhoods	Primary
			(1000)	White %		Catchments
41180	St. Louis	MO	2805	73	228	323
44700	Stockton	CA	732	32	60	119
45060	Syracuse	NY	654	81	61	84
45300	Tampa-St. Petersburg-Clearwater	FL	3030	63	267	255
45780	Toledo	OH	645	75	58	83
46060	Tucson	AZ	1019	52	85	113
46140	Tulsa	OK	985	65	89	167
46520	Urban Honolulu	HI	987	18	87	122
47260	Virginia Beach-Norfolk-Newport News	VA	1758	55	145	208
47900	Washington-Arlington-Alexandria	DC	6151	45	530	760
48620	Wichita	KS	636	72	56	118
49180	Winston-Salem	NC	661	68	53	64
49340	Worcester	MA	938	77	55	82
49660	Youngstown-Warren-Boardman	OH	545	83	44	57